

Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

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Type

- R** Document report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
- OTHER**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN** Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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1.0	Leaflet and accompanying report on its content and design	23.02.2023

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Publishable executive summary

BioReCer aims to ensure the environmental performance and traceability of biological feedstock used by the bio-based industries. This will be executed through the deployment of guidelines to strengthen current certification schemes. Within this approach, the added value, the use, as well as the social acceptance of bioproducts will be increased.

BioReCer targets different stakeholder groups with different viewpoints and needs concerning dissemination and communication. Besides online/digital measures and tools, also material for offline and/or hybrid activities are needed. These include e.g. banners, material for trade fair booths and project leaflets. This report describes the first version of the BioReCer leaflet which is also part of Milestone M10.

1 Project leaflet

A leaflet is a meaningful medium that supports communication of a project by presenting the core messages in a short, intriguing, visually and haptically appealing way. Furthermore, a leaflet easily and concisely explains the workflow and the setup of a project by not going too deep into detail; instead, it should act as a teaser to enter into a conversation, to encourage discussion and to trigger the wish to visit the project website.

Field of application for leaflets:

- Supports entering into a personal conversation by handing over the leaflet,
- Serves as eye-catcher at a conference/trade fair booth,
- Can be taken away from a booth to serve as memory aid,
- Can be added to a conference folder or a press kit,
- Can be sent in a letter due to its format,
- Can be appended as pdf to an email,
- Can be downloaded on a website.

1.1 Leaflet content

The front page shows the acronym "BioReCer", the full title of the project and the link to the BioReCer website.

The back page contains the general project information, i.e. funding statement and EU logo, project coordinator and partner logos, the project run-time and the QR code leading to the project website.

The first inner page when unfolding the leaflet contains a graphical element and explains the background and workflow of BioReCer. The opposite page describes the objectives of BioReCer.

The centre of the inner DinA4 page of the leaflet is the infographic of the project which is surrounded by explanatory text and the description of the BioReCer methodology (BRIE-LL and the four European case studies).

1.2 Leaflet layout

The leaflet is in DinA4 format folded two times to receive 6 individual pages and is based on the BioReCer colour code. Due to the lack of provided graphical elements and photos from the consortium, we decided for a different but non the less striking design derived from the logo; e.g. the front-page design with the colourful swirl is derived from the logo, and also the miniature project logo is used as design element for the bullet points. The graphical elements are commercially available stock photos.

Figure 1: Impression BioReCer leaflet outside DinA4 page

Background

A circular economy is sustainable if it is able to minimise waste and simultaneously maximise value from (organic) waste materials.

To realise this goal, organic waste materials require sufficient assessment. Further, the tracking and traceability of biological feedstock need to be guaranteed, and the respective bio-based value chains must be certified in a practical way.

However, current certification schemes need to be strengthened since not all of them sufficiently meet the specific requirements of organic resources.

BioReCer Course of Action

BioReCer will establish standardisation guidelines to strengthen current certification schemes. This will be done by developing a multidimensional assessment framework, which will allow an aggregated analysis of biological resources and their associated value chains.

BioReCer will test and evaluate the developed framework via integration into existing certification schemes. The methodologies of BioReCer will be validated by the BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living-Lab (BRIE-LL).

BioReCer

Data Gathering
Status Quo of Main Biological Resources Flows
Gaps, Barriers, Legal Requirements

Multi-dimensional Assessment Framework
Environmental & Traceability Assessment of Biological Resources and their Value Chains

BRIE-LL

BRSP
Mobilisation & Networking in Physical Meetings via Participatory Group Activities (e.g. Trainings)

Evaluation & Validation in 4 Case Studies

Fishery
Spain

Urban Biowaste
Italy

BIT
Key Information on Sustainability and Traceability of Biological Resources and their Value Chains

Agriculture
Greece

Forestry
Sweden

Guidelines

Strengthened Certification Schemes
Application in EU and globally

The BioReCer Innovation Eco-system Living-Lab (BRIE-LL)

For the assessment of environmental sustainability and tracking and traceability of biological resources, BioReCer will develop the innovative digital web portal BRIE-LL. It functions both as a virtual meeting place for the BioResources Stakeholders Platform (BRSP) and as a BioReCer ICT tool (BIT).

BRIE-LL will mobilise the BRSP through participatory group activities (e.g. workshops, networking and training capsules), while BIT is an auto-evaluation tool based on several machine and deep learning algorithms that provide stakeholders with key information on the environmental performance of bio-based value chains.

Case Studies

BioReCer will evaluate and validate the multi-dimensional assessment framework by BRIE-LL with four case studies in different EU countries.

These were selected based on their geographical distribution, biomass type and source, and associated bio-based value chains.

Case Study 1:
Fish caning industry and urban/industrial sewage sludge in Galicia, Spain.

Case Study 2:
Urban biowaste and wastewater from biorefineries in Lombardia, Italy.

Case Study 3:
Agricultural waste in Central Macedonia, Greece.

Case Study 4:
Residual streams from the forest industry in Västernorrland, Sweden.

Figure 2: Impression BioReCer leaflet inside DinA4 page

2 Conclusion

This is the first leaflet version that was designed for the BioReCer project. It will be updated with results and insights in the second half of the project.

The deliverable D8.3 was finished and submitted in time by nova-Institut with ongoing support and feedback of the entire BioReCer consortium and project coordinator Cetaqua.

3 List of abbreviations

BRIE-LL	BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living Lab
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